

Systematic Review on Role of Machine Learning in development of Perovskite Solar Cell

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ABSTRACT

The rapid advancement of Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) has garnered significant attention in the field of renewable energy. Perovskite solar cells offer a promising alternative to traditional silicon-based solar cells due to their high efficiency, ease of fabrication, and low production costs. However, challenges such as long-term stability, scalability, and device performance optimization remain. Recent advancements in machine learning (ML) techniques have demonstrated potential in addressing these challenges by providing predictive models, enhancing material discovery, optimizing fabrication processes, and improving device performance. This systematic review investigates the role of machine learning in the development of PSCs, exploring how ML is integrated into various stages of PSC research, from materials design to performance prediction. The review highlights the applications, methodologies, challenges, and future directions of ML in PSC research.

KEYWORDS: *Perovskite Solar Cell, Machine Learning (ML), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Deep learning (DL), Neural networks (NN).*

1. INTRODUCTION

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have emerged as a promising candidate for next-generation solar energy conversion due to their impressive power conversion efficiencies (PCE) and cost-effectiveness in manufacturing (Das et al., 2024 and Barik et al., (2024). Over the past decade, research has accelerated to address the challenges of stability, scalability, and efficiency, especially as the field has matured from lab-scale demonstrations to real-world applications (H. S. Das, 2025).

Machine learning (ML), a subset of artificial intelligence (AI), has proven to be a powerful tool in materials science, especially in the development of novel materials for energy applications (Xie, L., et al. (2021 and Li, J., et al. (2020). In the context of PSCs, ML can accelerate the discovery of new materials, optimize device architecture, and enhance manufacturing processes (Shi, L., et al. (2021 and Chen, C., et al. (2020). This review systematically examines the impact of ML in perovskite solar cell research, focusing on the ways in which ML techniques are integrated into the development pipeline.

Early Developments (2009-2012): Initial perovskite-based solar cells had low efficiencies (~3.8%) and suffered from stability issues due to liquid electrolytes (Y. Zhang et al.,(2018). Transition to Solid-State (2012-2015): The introduction of solid-state hole transport layers (HTLs) significantly improved efficiency and stability. Material Optimization (2015-2018): Mixed halide and cation engineering enhanced thermal and moisture stability, pushing efficiency above 20% (Priyanka Roy et al, (2020). Tandem Solar Cells (2018-2023): The combination of perovskite with silicon in tandem configurations broke the 29% efficiency barrier. Lead-Free and Printable PSCs (2023): Research focuses on environmentally friendly and scalable solutions with efficiencies above 25%. Table.1 shows the efficiency improvement of Perovskite solar cell.

Table 1. Efficiency Table of Perovskite Solar Cells

Year	Perovskite Composition	Device Structure	Efficiency (%)	Key Advancements
2009	CH ₃ NH ₃ PbI ₃ (MAPbI ₃)	Liquid-electrolyte DSSC	~3.8	First demonstration of perovskite-based solar cells.
2012	MAPbI ₃ /TiO ₂	Solid-state structure	~9.7	Solid-state HTL introduced, improving stability.
2015	(FAPbI ₃) _{0.8} (MAPbBr ₃) _{0.2}	Planar heterojunction	~20.1	Mixed perovskites enhance stability and efficiency.
2018	Cs _{0.05} (FA _{0.8} MA _{0.2})Pb(I _{1-x} Br _x) ₃	Inverted (p-i-n)	~23.3	Cs-doping enhances stability and efficiency.
2021	2D/3D Hybrid Perovskite	Tandem (Perovskite/Silicon)	~29.5	Improved band alignment in tandem cells.
2023	Sn-Pb Mixed Perovskite	Fully printable PSC	~25.6	Lead-free, eco-friendly alternatives explored.

1.1. Basics of Perovskite Solar Cell

A Perovskite solar cell (PSC) utilizes a material with a Perovskite structure as the light absorber to convert sunlight into electricity. When the sun's rays hit the Perovskite layer, electrons become excited, resulting in the formation of electron-hole pairs. Fig.1 shows the Schematic diagram of Perovskite solar cells. The transparent conductive oxide (TCO) anode is the destination for electrons directed by the electron transport layer (ETL), whereas holes are transported to the metal cathode by the hole transport layer (HTL). This separation of charge produces a photocurrent that moves through an external circuit to supply power. With their high efficiency, low-cost fabrication, and tunable bandgaps, PSCs are a promising alternative to traditional photovoltaics (Das et al., 2024). Nonetheless, two essential obstacles to commercialization are stability and scalability.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of Perovskite solar cells

1.2. Perovskite materials For Solar Cells

Perovskite materials have emerged as promising candidates for high-efficiency solar cells due to their excellent optoelectronic properties. These materials, typically based on the ABX₃ structure, where A is an organic/inorganic cation, B is a metal (Pb, Sn), and X is a halide (I, Br, Cl), offer high absorption coefficients, tunable bandgaps, and long carrier diffusion lengths. Advancements in hybrid organic-inorganic perovskites have led to efficiencies exceeding 25%, rivaling silicon solar cells. However,

challenges like stability, toxicity (Pb content), and scalability remain. Ongoing research focuses on lead-free alternatives, interface engineering, and encapsulation techniques to enhance durability and commercial viability.

2. METHODOLOGY AND WORKFLOW OF ML

The workflow of Machine Learning (ML) involves several key steps. It begins with data collection, where relevant datasets are gathered. Next, data preprocessing is performed to clean, transform, and prepare the data. Then, feature engineering selects or creates important features. The model selection phase involves choosing an appropriate algorithm. The training step fits the model to the data, followed by evaluation using test datasets. If needed, hyperparameter tuning is conducted to optimize performance. Once satisfactory, the model undergoes deployment in real-world applications. Finally, monitoring and maintenance ensure continuous improvement and adaptation to new data trends.

The Machine Learning (ML) workflow for Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) begins with data collection, including experimental and simulated datasets on material properties, device performance, and environmental stability. Data pre-processing involves cleaning, normalization, and feature selection. Feature engineering extracts critical parameters like bandgap, defect density, and stability factors. Model selection (e.g., neural networks, regression models) is followed by training on historical PSC data. Evaluation ensures accuracy using test sets, while hyper-parameter tuning optimizes performance. Once validated, the model aids in predictive analysis for efficiency enhancement. Finally, deployment enables real-time material discovery, process optimization, and long-term performance prediction. Role of Machine Learning in the Development of Perovskite Solar Cell (PSCs) are shown in Table.2.

Table 2. Role of Machine Learning in the Development of Perovskite Solar Cells (PSCs)

Stage	Description
Research Question Formulation	Define key questions focusing on how ML contributes to PSC efficiency, stability, and material optimization.
Literature Search Strategy	Identify databases (e.g., Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect) and use keywords like "Machine Learning," "Perovskite Solar Cells," "Optimization," "Stability."
Inclusion & Exclusion Criteria	Include peer-reviewed articles (2015–present), studies on ML applications in PSCs, and exclude irrelevant/non-technical papers.
Study Selection Process	Screen abstracts and full texts based on relevance and methodological rigor.
Data Extraction	Extract details on ML techniques (e.g., Neural Networks, Genetic Algorithms, Decision Trees) and their impact on PSC properties.
Quality Assessment	Evaluate study reliability using standard quality-check frameworks (e.g., PRISMA).
Data Synthesis	Categorize findings into efficiency prediction, material discovery, and degradation analysis.
Discussion & Conclusion	Analyze trends, limitations, and future research directions for ML in PSCs.

3. APPLICATIONS OF MACHINE LEARNING IN PSC DEVELOPMENT

3.1. Material Discovery and Optimization

One of the primary challenges in PSC development is the identification of stable, efficient, and cost-effective materials. Machine learning models, particularly deep learning (DL) and reinforcement learning (RL), have been used to predict the properties of new materials and their suitability for PSCs.

ML for Bandgap Prediction: Accurate prediction of bandgap is critical for material selection (Jeffrey Kirman et al.,2020). ML models can predict the electronic properties of Perovskite materials by training on

large datasets containing known material properties. For example, support vector machines (SVM) and random forest algorithms have been employed to predict the bandgap of potential Perovskite candidates.

Stability Prediction: The long-term stability of PSCs remains a key concern. ML models have been used to predict the stability of Perovskite materials under various environmental conditions. This allows researchers to identify promising materials that could potentially exhibit enhanced durability. Fig.2 shows the development process of Perovskite Solar Cell through Machine Learning.

Figure 2. Development of Perovskite Solar Cell through Machine Learning.

3.2. Device Performance Prediction

ML has been extensively used to predict the performance of PSC devices based on a combination of material properties and processing conditions. Regression techniques, including neural networks (NN) and support vector regression (SVR), have been used to model and predict power conversion efficiency (PCE) from various input parameters, such as layer thickness, material composition, and deposition method (Nikhil Shrivastav et al.,2024).

Surrogate Models: These models are trained on experimental data to provide fast, approximate solutions to complex physical simulations. Surrogate models can replace time-consuming simulations and assist in optimizing PSC design and performance.

Optimization of Device Architecture: Machine learning models have been applied to design optimized layer structures in PSCs. By analyzing experimental data, ML algorithms can recommend ideal thicknesses and configurations for charge transport layers, light absorption layers, and electron-hole interfaces.

3.3. Process Optimization and Manufacturing

The fabrication process for PSCs plays a significant role in determining their efficiency and scalability. ML techniques, such as supervised learning, can optimize fabrication parameters, including solvent

composition, temperature, and deposition speed, to achieve uniform and high-quality films (Aarif UI Islam Shah et al.,2025).

Process Control and Monitoring: ML can assist in monitoring real-time data from fabrication processes, ensuring consistent and repeatable results. For example, ML models have been used to predict the optimal conditions for spin-coating, which is a common method for producing perovskite films (Jieqiong Liu et al., (2024).

Automated Quality Control: Vision-based ML systems, often employing convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have been used to inspect the quality of fabricated films and identify defects that could impair device performance.

3.4. Accelerating Research and Development

ML enables accelerated discovery by automating routine tasks, such as screening large datasets of material properties or simulating PSC performance. High-throughput experimental setups combined with ML models have led to a reduction in time and resources required for research.

4. CHALLENGES IN INTEGRATING MACHINE LEARNING WITH PSC RESEARCH

While machine learning has shown promise in enhancing PSC development, several challenges need to be addressed:

Data Availability and Quality: ML models rely on large, high-quality datasets. The lack of standardized, high-quality datasets in PSC research is a significant barrier to the widespread adoption of ML techniques.
Model Interpretability: Many ML models, particularly deep learning approaches, operate as "black boxes," making it difficult to understand the underlying physical mechanisms. Interpretability remains a critical issue in material science applications.

Generalization Across Different Systems: Models trained on specific materials or device architectures may not generalize well to other systems, limiting their usefulness.

Integration with Existing Experimental Methods: Incorporating ML into existing research workflows requires significant changes in experimental design and data collection methods, which may require substantial investment in infrastructure and expertise.

5. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The future of ML in PSC development lies in the continued integration of AI-driven approaches with experimental methods. Some promising future directions include:

Transfer Learning: Leveraging knowledge from other material systems to improve models for Perovskite materials.

AI-Driven Design: Autonomous systems where ML models iteratively design and optimize materials and devices in a closed-loop fashion.

Integration with Quantum Simulations: Combining ML with quantum mechanical simulations to better predict material properties at the atomic level.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Machine learning has proven to be a valuable tool in accelerating the development of perovskite solar cells, offering improvements in material discovery, performance prediction, and process optimization.

However, challenges related to data quality, model interpretability, and generalization remain. By overcoming these challenges, machine learning has the potential to play an even greater role in advancing PSC technology, ultimately contributing to the realization of highly efficient, stable, and scalable solar energy solutions.

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